

Common DEPs GO CC Enrichment Analysis

Downregulated | Significant genes: 65 | Top 5 pathways

$-\log_{10} p.\text{adj}$

0.0 2.5 5.0 7.5

Gene Count

● 5 ● 10 ● 15 ● 20